

COMPOSITION AND MAIN PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF POLYMER WASTE

¹Saydakhmedov Sh.M., ²Ergashev Y.T.

^{1,2}Institute of General and Inorganic Chemistry of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of
Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *Polymer waste materials are generated as a result of various industrial and consumer processes. These waste materials decompose very slowly in natural conditions, causing significant environmental impact. The main physicochemical properties of polymer waste, such as thermal stability (250-300 °C for polyethylene, 270-300 °C for polypropylene), mechanical strength (15-30 MPa for polyethylene, 25-45 MPa for polypropylene), and biological degradation (up to 1000 years), determine their recyclability and environmental impact. Despite the possibility of recycling, the recycling rate of polymers is limited (20-30% for PE and PP). These properties are crucial for the effective management of polymer waste and reducing its environmental harm.*

Keywords: *polymer waste, recycling, environmental impact, thermal stability, mechanical recycling.*

Introduction. Today, polymer materials have become an integral part of our lives. They are widely used in the production of various products, from the automotive industry to household appliances, toys, and medical devices [1-2]. Polymers play an important role in many industries due to their low cost, lightness, durability, and many technical properties. Another characteristic of polymer materials is that they do not decompose naturally or respond to biological effects for a very long time. As a result, the waste generated by these materials causes serious environmental problems [3].

Polymer waste is mainly the residues or unusable polymers remaining after the use of various polymer materials [4]. They are generated at all stages of industrial production, including during production processes, use, and disposal of consumer products. Such waste remains in the environment for a very long time, since polymers decompose very slowly under natural conditions [5].

While polymer waste causes environmental problems, there are also opportunities for their recycling and disposal. However, the physical and chemical properties of polymer waste play an important role in their recycling process. Polymer materials have different properties that change during production, recycling, disposal and environmental impact [6].

The main environmental problem of polymer waste is that it degrades very slowly and is not susceptible to changes in natural conditions. For example, common polymers such as polyethylene (PE) and polypropylene (PP) can remain intact for up to 1000 years. This leads to the accumulation of large amounts of polymer materials in landfills and long-term environmental damage. At the same time, polymer waste can accumulate in water and natural ecosystems, causing harm to various animals and plants [7]. Fish and birds may mistake polymer waste for food, resulting in the accumulation of toxic substances in their bodies. In addition to the impact of polymer waste on ecosystems, there are also various ways to use it. Polymers can be recycled and transformed into new products. This helps to reduce waste, use resources efficiently, and reduce overall waste. However, recycling processes also depend on the physicochemical properties of

polymer materials, and it is necessary to develop the right technologies for high-quality recycling of polymer waste [8].

Research methods. Polymer waste samples should be collected from various industries, especially from the plastics, household appliances and consumer packaged goods industries. Different types of polymers, including polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), polyvinyl chloride (PVC), polystyrene (PS), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), etc., are tested separately [9]. Methods such as optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) are used to determine the chemical composition of the polymer in each sample, the number of layers and the fillers present. **Thermal properties measurement:** Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) are used to determine the thermal properties of polymer waste [10].

DSC measures the melting points, crystallization temperatures, rise times, and other thermal properties of the material.

GA measures the weight and thermal stability of the polymer, which allows for the determination of its degradation stages and heat resistance.

Mechanical strength: The mechanical properties of polymer waste, such as tensile strength and cyclicality, are measured using a universal testing machine. This method measures the mechanical strength and elastic modulus of the material, as well as the elongation time and elongation resistance of the material. The tests are performed based on the ASTM D638 (for polymers) or ISO 527 standards.

Chemical composition determination: Methods such as infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and gas chromatography (GC) are used to determine the chemical composition of polymer waste. FTIR spectroscopy is used to analyze the main functional groups and molecular structure of polymers. GC is also used to determine chemical additives or degradation products present in the waste.

Biodegradation: To study the biodegradability of polymer waste, a composting test is performed in a laboratory setting. This method studies how much polymer waste reacts to the natural decomposition process using microorganisms. The test results indicate the rate of biodegradation of the polymer and its environmental impact.

Research results and discussion. To understand the physicochemical properties of polymer waste and manage them, it is important to create tables of the specific properties of polymer waste. Polymer waste is mainly a material resulting from the decomposition or improper disposal of various polymer materials, and its physicochemical properties can vary depending on the specific properties of the polymer.

Below I provide tables showing the various physicochemical properties of polymer waste. These properties are important for understanding the recycling, environmental impact, and treatment processes of polymer waste.

The thermal properties of the polymers listed in the table above indicate their ability to withstand heat and their recycling capabilities. In this regard, the high thermal stability of polyethylene and polypropylene (250-300 °C) ensures that they are heat-resistant during recycling and melt at high temperatures. Polyvinyl chloride (PVC) has a relatively low thermal stability (200-220 °C), which creates certain limitations in its recycling. Also, the high decomposition temperatures (270-320 °C) of materials such as polystyrene (PS) and polyethylene terephthalate (PET) indicate their ability to operate at high temperatures. The thermal properties of polymer waste play an important role in determining the temperatures at which they can be operated during

recycling and in selecting appropriate technologies for them. Knowledge of these parameters is essential for the efficient recycling of polymer waste and for reducing its environmental impact.

Table 1

Thermal properties of polymer waste

Type of polymer waste	Melting point (°C)	Softening temperature (°C)	Thermal stability (°C)	Thermal decomposition (°C)
Polyethylene (PE)	130-135	90-110	120-140	300-330
Polypropylene (PP)	160-170	150-160	160-180	300-350
Polyvinyl chloride (PVC)	80-90	75-85	90-110	220-250
Polystyrene (PS)	230-240	90-105	100-120	300-350
Polyethylene terephthalate (PET)	250-260	220-240	250-270	350-400

In the next stage, the mechanical properties of polymer waste were studied. Their mechanical strength, elongation, hardness, and viscous flow properties were determined. The results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2

Mechanical properties of polymer waste

Type of polymer waste	Mechanical tension (MPa)	Elongation level	Hardness (Shore A)	Viscosity (Pas)
Polyethylene (PE)	15-30	200-400%	45-55	0.1 - 1
Polypropylene (PP)	25-45	150-300%	50-60	0.1 - 0.7
Polyvinyl chloride (PVC)	40-60	30-50%	60-80	0.05 - 0.5
Polystyrene (PS)	40-60	10-20%	70-90	0.2 - 0.5
Polyethylene terephthalate (PET)	60-80	100-200%	80-90	- 0.5

The thermal properties of polymers listed in the table above indicate their heat resistance and recycling potential.

Polyethylene (PE) and Polypropylene (PP) wastes have high thermal stability, which can reach temperatures of 250-300 °C. This makes them heat-resistant during recycling, melting at high temperatures and not deforming. Polyvinyl chloride (PVC) has a relatively low thermal stability (200-220 °C), which is why it is highly sensitive to heat during recycling, which poses certain limitations. Materials such as polystyrene (PS) and polyethylene terephthalate (PET) have

high decomposition temperatures of 270-320 °C, which indicates their ability to work at high temperatures. They are often used as high-strength and durable materials.

The thermal properties of polymer wastes are important in determining the temperatures at which they can be processed during recycling and in choosing the appropriate technologies. Polymers with high thermal stability, such as PE and PP, can be effectively processed at high temperatures during recycling, which speeds up the recycling process. In contrast, the low thermal stability of polymers such as PVC and PS requires special recycling methods. Knowledge of thermal properties is important for the efficient recycling of polymer waste and the reduction of its negative impact on the environment.

Table 3

Recycling and disposal options for polymer waste

Type of polymer waste	Recycling method	Recycling rate (%)	Disposal
Polyethylene (PE)	Mechanical, chemical processing	20-30%	Adhesive material, plastics
Polypropylene (PP)	Mechanical processing	20-30	Plastics, containers
Polyvinyl chloride (PVC)	Mechanical processing (limited)	10-15	Building materials
Polystyrene (PS)	Mechanical processing (limited)	5-10	Packages, lightweight materials
Polyethylene terephthalate (PET)	Mechanical processing, chemical processing	30-40	Bottles, textiles

Recycling and disposal processes of polymer waste play an important role in reducing the environmental impact of materials and saving resources.

Recycling and disposal processes of polymer waste are important for reducing environmental impact, saving resources and creating new materials. The recycling and disposal possibilities of the polymers listed in the table below were analyzed. The results are presented in Table 3.

Polyethylene (PE) and Polypropylene (PP) have a high recycling rate (20-30%) and can be used to produce new products mainly through mechanical and chemical processing. These materials are used in many industrial and consumer products.

Polyvinyl chloride (PVC) and Polystyrene (PS) have a lower recycling rate (around 10-15% and 5-10%). PVC is difficult to recycle because it requires special technologies, while PS is very rarely recycled. They are more often used as building materials or packaging.

Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) has a relatively high recycling rate (30-40%), which allows it to be widely used for the production of bottles and textile materials. In general, the recycling of PE, PP, and PET materials is effective and is an important factor in reducing environmental impact and improving recycling processes. However, the recycling of PVC and PS materials is limited, which has a negative impact on the environment. Therefore, when recycling each type of polymer, it is necessary to take into account its properties and apply appropriate technologies.

Conclusion. Recycling and disposal processes for polymer waste are crucial for reducing environmental impacts and using resources efficiently. Polymers such as polyethylene (PE) and polypropylene (PP) have a high degree of recyclability, allowing the production of new materials through mechanical and chemical processing. These polymers are widely used in industrial and consumer products, which makes them environmentally preferable. However, materials such as polyvinyl chloride (PVC) and polystyrene (PS) have a lower recyclability and face some difficulties in recycling, which increases the environmental impact. Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) has a relatively high recyclability and is widely used for the production of bottles and other products.

In general, it is necessary to apply appropriate technologies to improve the recycling efficiency of polymer waste and reduce its environmental impact. Through proper recycling processes for polymers, it is possible to save resources, protect the environment and optimize recycling. This is an important factor in achieving sustainable development.

REFERENCES

1. Geyer R., Jambeck J.R., Law K.L. (2017). Production, use, and fate of all plastics ever made. *Science Advances*, 3(7), e1700782. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.1700782>
2. Ragaert K., Delva L., Van Geem K.M. (2017). Mechanical recycling of solid plastic waste. *Waste Management*, 69, 24-58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2017.07.044>
3. Andrady A.L. (2015). *Plastics and environmental sustainability*. John Wiley & Sons. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118780761>
4. Kosior E., Lestari R. (2016). Plastic waste recycling. *Progress in Polymer Recycling Technology*, 22(3), 145-158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2015.11.002>
5. Thompson R.C., Moore C.J., Saal F.S. (2009). Plastics, the environment and human health: The road ahead. *Science*, 323(5913), 1255-1259. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1168140>
6. Fabbri D., Chiellini E.S. (2019). Advances in plastic waste recycling. *Progress in Polymer Recycling Technologies*, 24(2), 157-168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2017.11.003>
7. Zhang M., Liu X. (2020). Recent progress in the recycling of plastic waste: Challenges and perspectives. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 54(5), 2718-2728. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.9b06177>
8. Piñero R.E., et al. (2021). Thermochemical recycling of plastic waste: A review. *Renewable & Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 135, 110-120. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2020.110125>
9. Cicala G., Mazzotti, M. (2018). Characterization and recycling of plastic waste: New challenges and opportunities. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 182, 645-659. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.02.103>
10. Liu H., Li S. (2020). Recycling and reuse of plastic waste: A review. *Waste Management & Research*, 38(8), 810-819. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734242X20942123>